

CHARACTERISATION OF VOIDS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON DAMAGE PROPAGATION IN RESIN INFUSED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

High-performance structural composite components have historically been most often manufactured with prepreg materials cured in an autoclave oven. To remain cost-competitive, it is generally assumed that in the future an increasing fraction of parts will be manufactured with a faster, less expensive process such as liquid composite moulding (LCM). The weakness of LCM processes is the generally higher void content compared with prepreg and autoclave processing, due to entrapment of bubbles during infusion. The effect of voids on the resulting mechanical properties is still relatively unclear, especially for heterogeneous void distributions, which is always the case in LCM. Intuitively it is expected that void parameters such as size, shape, location, clustering, and local concentration would play a role in damage development and failure, but their relative effects are currently not well understood. A better understanding of these micromechanisms could ideally give some indications as to how to suppress damage formation and improve the mechanical performance.

This study focuses on the formation of voids in resin transfer moulded carbon fibre reinforced polymers and their effect on damage development that ultimately leads to final failure. This was done by characterising voids in the resin of the cured laminates using X-ray computed tomography (CT), and by looking at the material failure mechanisms associated with in-plane and out-of-plane behaviour. Laminate coupons were tested under low cycle tension fatigue and low velocity out-of-plane impact/indentation. The void distribution was found to be heterogeneous with voids nucleating in plies where the fibre orientation was not parallel to the flow direction, at the ply interfaces, and along woven yarns. In out-of-plane loading, multiple cracks/delaminations were seen to interact with these void regions. As a consequence of increased loading, these delaminations grew and coalesced with their neighbours to form a single larger delamination prior to final failure. In open-hole, in-plane tension fatigue testing, larger voids resulted in delaminations initiating at the void. Transverse (out-of-plane) cracks are seen to form around smaller voids.

1 INTRODUCTION

Much of the high-performance composites industry is currently investigating the possibility of switching from the use of prepreg materials to liquid composite moulding (LCM). LCM processes such as resin transfer moulding (RTM) are promising due to lower costs than prepreg-based processing. A significant challenge in LCM is the higher void content. Even with a properly degassed resin matrix system, low volatiles, and a good pressure seal on the moulding cavity, voids form through entrapment of bubbles as the resin moves through the tortuous fibre architecture of the reinforcement [1, 2]. Conversion to LCM processing would be facilitated by developing a deeper understanding of how these bubbles form, bubble mobility during the early part of the cure process, and the mechanisms behind how the resultant voids decrease the load-at-failure for the laminate. With models based on such an understanding, the process conditions, ply lay-up, and mould configuration for an LCM process could be optimised to meet mechanical requirements with minimised material and processing costs.

Void formation and mobility have been the study of recent fluid mechanics studies [3, 4]. The effects of voids on mechanical properties and damage development have been studied for a longer period of time [5-9]. Voids are known to have deleterious effects on the mechanical performance of composites, especially on toughness-related parameters [10, 11]. However, these studies mostly focus on homogeneous void distributions in well-defined prepreg-based laminates. Only a few studies focus on the effects of voids formed during LCM processing on the mechanical performance of composites [11-13]. The lack of documented research on this topic is due to the historical predominance of prepreg for high-performance composites, as well as the general difficulty in characterising laminate properties and correlating them with the heterogeneous void distribution due to LCM. The heterogeneous void distribution in LCM manufactured composites results from the characteristic pressure gradient during preform impregnation. This pressure gradient drives the resin flow from one part of the mould to another, and also causes movement of bubbles in the matrix from the high pressure at the resin inlet towards the lower pressure at the flow front or mould vent. Furthermore, the pressure gradient varies during the course of mould filling [14]. As LCM is receiving increased attention for high-performance composites, the need to develop better tools to characterise the local void properties and resulting failure mechanisms in a laminate becomes more and more critical.

This study focuses on the formation of voids in RTM carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP), and the effects of those voids on damage development that ultimately leads to final failure. This was done by characterising voids in the matrix of CFRP laminates using x-ray computed tomography (CT), and by applying and correlating statistical metrics with material failure mechanisms associated with in-plane (fatigue) and out-of-plane (impact/indentation) behaviour. The purpose of this work is to provide a brief overview on the types of voids present in the RTM materials and its interaction on damage mechanisms on a variety of loading test configurations. Analysis of the acquired data is currently ongoing, and forthcoming publications are expected to give a more comprehensive understanding.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Quasi-isotropic $[0/-45/90/+45]_{2s}$ laminates were manufactured by RTM. Hexcel's HexFlow RTM6 was used to infuse a uni-directional (UD) carbon-fibre weave. The fabric architecture consists of UD carbon fibre tows held together by biaxial woven fibreglass yarns. This architecture results in a more convoluted path for the transportation of gas bubbles during infusion than in the more typically studied UD non-stitched prepreg reinforcement case. The infusion was uni-directional, along the 0° axis of the laminate, so that the ply lay-up denotes the angle between the flow direction and the carbon tows in each ply. The average fibre volume fraction for the laminates was 53%.

Imaging by micro-focus x-ray CT (μ X-CT) was conducted on the Nikon Metrology HMX 225 CT scanner at the University of Southampton's (England) μ -VIS Centre. A molybdenum target with no filtering was used. Synchrotron imaging was done by synchrotron-radiation computed tomography (SRCT) experiments performed on the TOMCAT/X02DA beamline at the Swiss Light Source (SLS), Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen, Switzerland. A 'match stick' shaped sample ($4 \times 4 \times 30$ mm region of interest) was mounted with a sample to detector propagation distance of 30 mm. The settings for μ X-CT and SRCT are shown in Table 1. The scans were reconstructed using a filtered back projection algorithm to form an 8-bit volume with voxel grey scale intensities ranging 0–255. Each sample and region of interest was scanned with both imaging facilities and no penetrants or any other treatment was applied to the specimen.

Laminate coupons were tested under low cycle tension fatigue and low velocity out-of-plane impact/quasi-static indentation (QSI), according to the ASTM standards. Damage propagation was captured at incremental load steps using both SRCT and μ X-CT. See Figure 1.

Table 1: Settings for CT scans.

Sample Geometry (mm)	Void evaluation $4 \times 30 \times 4$		Indent/Impact $100 \times 150 \times 4$ Tension Fatigue $25 \times 200 \times 4$
CT Scanner	SRCT	μX-CT	μX-CT
Energy (kV)	19 (monochromatic)	60 (peak)	115
Current (μ A)	–	134	100
Reconstruction size (px)	2000×2000	2000×2000	2000×2000
Voxel resolution (μm^3)	1.4	4.3	8
Number of radiographs	1500 (180°)	2000 (360°)	1301
Exposure time (ms)	100	1300	1000

Figure 1: Test procedure for (a-c) impact/QSI and (d-f) tension fatigue.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Void distribution

Figure 2 shows an example 3D volume generated by stitching together multiple 3D scans obtained by micro-focus x-CT imagery. The volume has approximate dimensions of $6 \times 4 \times 4$ mm ($x - y - z$). Both the matrix and carbon fibres (blue) have been segmented out of the images, to allow better visualisation of the voids (purple) and the fibreglass biaxial woven yarns (white and black). The orientation of each of the 16 fabric layers is denoted on the right-side axis for the entire z -direction thickness of the laminate. As seen in Figure 2 and further analysis of each 2D image slice, the void distribution was found to be heterogeneous with voids nucleating at three locations: (i) plies where the fibre orientation was not parallel to the flow direction (oblique to the 0° axis), (ii) at the ply interfaces, and (iii) along woven fibreglass yarns.

Figure 2: Results from μ X-CT showing segmentation of the material constituents.

The accumulation of voids at both carbon and fibreglass fibres when oriented at either 45° or 90° to the flow is suspected to be due to the greater propensity for bubble entrapment by the impeding fibres. Bubbles formed in non-crimped fabrics have been shown to become trapped along the stitching fibres in the bias directions to the flow [4, 15]. These same laminates have recently been characterised under fatigue loading, with the load applied in the same direction as the infusion. This study demonstrated that the sensitivity of transverse crack accumulation to voids also increases from 0° plies (orientation to both flow and load) through 45° plies and is maximal in the 90° plies [11]. More voids were shown to form in the plies transverse to the flow, and the voids are most deleterious when located in plies oriented transverse to the load. It would thus be worthwhile to consider to infuse in a direction parallel to the expected primary load direction, thereby limiting void formation in the more damage-sensitive transverse plies.

3.2 Quasi-static indentation/impact loading

Impact on composite surfaces is a key problem in aircraft applications. The first case concerns indentation in the through-thickness direction, which can generate similar damage to impact [16-18]. Although of lesser relevance, this related loading mode allowed better control of the experiment and observation of damage accumulation during increased indentation. Under quasi-static indentation (QSI) loading, multiple cracks/delaminations were seen to interact with these regions of high void content (Figure 1b). This is likely due to the elongated shape of the voids in the plane of the composite plate. As the QSI load increased, out-of-plane (through-thickness) intra-ply cracks began to form directly under the indentation, in the ply farthest from the indentation. These cracks formed at the same time as the onset of delamination at the ply interface in contact with the transverse ply cracks. The delamination starts between voids located near the fibreglass biaxial yarns. The delaminations grow and coalesce with increased indentation, eventually leading to a large overall delamination prior to final failure.

Figure 1c shows a 3D volume obtained by splicing multiple 3D scans, where half of the sample on one side of the centre-indentation shows all fibres and matrix, and the other half was segmented to remove the matrix and carbon fibres, leaving only the voids / delamination and the fibreglass yarns. This shows that the orientation of the delamination follows the architecture of the fibreglass yarns and the voids. An overlay of the cracked zones for different indent depths (Figure 3a) reveals, that apart from voids, delamination also takes place around the binding yarns where there are less voids. This was also observed in the orthogonal views of four different laminate coupons impacted at a range of energies (Figure 3b). Whereas the orientation of the various layers is known to affect the driving force for delamination in well-defined prepreg materials (e.g. [19]), this effect may be overshadowed by the presence binding yarns and the void concentrations found in their vicinity.

Figure 3: Arrows indicate indenter location in μ X-CT imaging for (a) QSI tests (top view) and (b) impact tests (orthogonal views).

3.3 Open-hole in-plane tension fatigue testing

In the next case study, damage accumulation during in-plane tensile fatigue was investigated. The localised stress concentration from the partial open hole facilitates observation of damage formation and accumulation. Figure 1d-f shows x-ray CT scans after progressively increasing numbers of fatigue tension cycles of an open-hole coupon, both observed from above the sample on the x - y in-plane surface (left side) and on the sample cross-section (right side). Again, the carbon fibres and matrix are segmented away to only display the voids, cracks, delamination, and fibreglass yarns. One can again see the orientation of the voids corresponding to accumulation at the fibreglass yarns, especially at the intersections between the biaxial yarns. The cracks due to fatigue loading are almost all located in the inter-ply resin region, and only between non- 0° plies. The driving force for tunnelling transverse cracks is known to diminish for plies with smaller orientation angles (e.g. [20]). Qualitatively, the largest voids in the material system studied leads to delamination initiation. Quantification of the critical size and shape will be undertaken in future work.

Figure 4 shows the cross-sectional view with all material components for various cycle counts in the same open-hole tension fatigue coupon. The well-known pattern of increasing number of transverse cracks in the off-axis layers presents itself inside the material.

Figure 4: Orthogonal views from μ X-CT of an open-hole tension fatigue coupon after different numbers of load cycles (load applied along x-axis or direction of production).

4 CONCLUSIONS

X-ray computed tomography has been shown to be a useful tool in studying the 3D damage mechanisms in RTM manufactured laminates containing voids. This has been exemplified for both indentation into the laminate and in-plane tensile fatigue loading. The void distribution was found to be heterogeneous with voids nucleating in plies where the fibre orientation was oblique to the flow direction, at the ply interfaces, and along woven fibre yarns.

Under QSI loading, multiple cracks/delaminations were seen to interact with these regions. As the QSI load increased, these delaminations grew and coalesced with their neighbours to form a single larger delamination quickly leading to final failure.

Under in-plane tension fatigue testing, crack formation starts almost exclusively in the resin rich region between the plies, and only between obliquely oriented plies. Generally, larger voids increase the likelihood of delaminations initiating at the void. Transverse cracks are seen to form around smaller voids.

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